

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF SELF-MEDICATION AMONG THE
STUDENTS OF GUJRANWALA MEDICAL COLLEGE,
GUJRANWALA**¹Dr Sidra Saeed, ²Dr Tooba Sahar, ³Dr Jamshaid Akhtar, ⁴Dr Uswa E Hasna¹PHFMC run BHU²Shifa International Hospital, Islamabad³Jinnah Hospital Lahore⁴Mayo Hospital Lahore

Article Received: May 2020

Accepted: June 2020

Published: July 2020

Abstract:

Background: Self-medication is a human behavior in which an individual uses a substance or any exogenous influence to self-administer treatment for physical or psychological ailments. The most widely self-medicated substances are over-the-counter drugs used to treat common health issues at home, as well as dietary supplements. These don't require a doctor's prescription to obtain and, in some countries, are easily available in supermarkets and convenience stores.

Methods: A Cross Sectional study was conducted at Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala from May to June 2016, to Assess Self- Medication among students of Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala. In this regard a semi structured; pretested Questionnaire was used to get responses from 100 students of GMC by simple random sampling. And then data was analyzed by the software SPSS version 24.

Results: Of a total of 100 students, (99%) of them practiced self-medication. Most drugs for self-medication were obtained from the community pharmacies; and the most commonly used drug was Panadol. Commonly reported illness was fever (57.6%) followed by pains and sore throats (both 47.5%). Convenience was the top reported factors for self-medication. Indications for use (66.7%) was the top reported reason for self-medication.

Conclusion: In conclusion, self-medication was practiced with a range of drugs from the conventional analgesics to antibiotics. Although the practice of self-medication is inevitable; drug authorities and health professionals need to educate students about the pros and cons of self-medication.

Keywords: Self-medication, antibiotics, Gujranwala Medical College, medicine.

Corresponding author:

Dr Sidra Saeed,
PHFMC run BHU

QR code

Please cite this article in press Sidra Saeed et al, *Assessment Of Self-Medication Among The Students Of Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(07).*

INTRODUCTION:

Self-medication is the use of drugs with therapeutic intent but without professional advice or prescription. It has also been defined as the use of non-prescription medicines by people on their own initiative [1]. Generally speaking, self-medication is defined as "the use of drugs to treat self-diagnosed disorders or symptoms, or the intermittent or continued use of a prescribed drug for chronic or recurrent disease or symptoms. Drugs that are prone to self-medication include analgesics, antipyretics, antibiotics and cough syrups, among others [2]. Self-medication with antibiotics occur in many developing countries (including Pakistan) where drugs are not well-regulated and accounted for. Hence there is easier access to prescription or over-the-counter medicines without prescription. Self-medication, could cause wide spread bacterial resistance to such antibiotics and may precipitate the emergence of multiple resistant organisms that would be difficult to treat and this has caused increased morbidity and mortality rated [3-6]. Perception of illness and incessant advertising, among other factors, have increased the prevalence of self-medication which accounts for about 2.9 - 3.7 % causes of death in hospitals as a result of harmful drug-drug interactions [7-13].

Some of the problems associated with self-medication such as masked diagnoses, use of excessive drug dosage, prolonged duration of usage, drug-drug interactions, polypharmacy and super infection can occur in self-medicating individuals. However, there is substantial variation in the prevalence rates of self-medication among developing and developed nations due to inherent differences in cultural and socioeconomic factors, disparities in health care systems such as reimbursement policies, access to health care, and drug dispensing policies [14] and general awareness level. Self-medication is often seen as gaining personal independence from established medicine, and it can be seen as a human right, implicit in, or closely related to the right to refuse professional medical treatment. There is much public and professional concern about the irrational use of drugs. The prevalence rates are high all over the world; up to 68% in European countries, while much higher in the developing countries with rates going

Sample Size for Frequency in a Population

Population size (for finite population correction factor or fpc) (N):	500
Hypothesized % frequency of outcome factor in the population (p):	91% +/-5
Confidence limits as % of 100(absolute +/- %)(d):	5%
Design effect (for cluster surveys-DEFF):	1

as high as 92% in the adolescents of Kuwait. Our neighboring countries have a prevalence rate of 31% in India and 59% in Nepal. Very few studies regarding self-medication have been conducted in Pakistan which have also confirmed high rates of prevalence of around 51%. It is also alarming that the prevalence rates are on the rise despite efforts to limit this problem. Various previous studies have shown that self-medication practices are more common in women and in those; who live alone, have a lower socioeconomic status, have more chronic ailments, have psychiatric conditions, are of younger age and in students. Very few researches have been conducted to estimate the prevalence of self-medication practice among medical students. The present study was undertaken to identify the reasons for, and the patterns of, self-medication among medical students. The aim of this study is to assess the pattern of self-medication practice, commonly used medicines, factors responsible for self-medication and end result of this practice among undergraduate medical students.

Objectives of Study

1. To assess self-medication behaviors among the students of Gujranwala Medical College.
2. To study the factors responsible for self these behaviors

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design: Descriptive study

Study Area: Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala

Study Population: Students of Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala.

Study Duration: 1 month

Study Population: Students of Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala.

Inclusion Criteria: Students of Gujranwala Medical College and those who practice self-medication.

Exclusion Criteria: Students other than Gujranwala medical college and those who do not practice self-medication

Ethical Issue: All the subjects were explained the purpose and process of study. They were explained the benefits of study. Assurance was given to protect the privacy of human study subjects.

Sampling:

Size: 100

Sample Size(n) for Various Confidence Levels

Confidence	Level (%)	Sample Size
95%		100
80%		49
90%		76
97%		119
99%		152
99.9%		208
99.99%		250

Equation

$$\text{Sample size } n = \frac{DEFF * Np(1-p)}{[(d2/Z21-\alpha/2*(N-1)+p*(1-p)]}$$

Results from OpenEpi, Version 3

Technique: Non probability convenient sampling.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS PLAN:

Data collection tool: Semi structured, pretested Questionnaire was used to collect data.

Data analysis plan: By using the SPSS software version 24.

Results: Semi structured, pretested Questionnaire was used to collect data. Of a total of 100 students, (99%) of them practiced self-medication. Most drugs for self-medication were obtained from the community pharmacies; and the most commonly used drug was Panadol. Commonly reported illness was fever (57.6%) followed by pains and sore throats (both 47.5%). Convenience was the top reported factors for self-medication. Most common indication for use (66.7%) was the top reported reason for self-medication.

Table 1.0: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	63	63.0
Male	37	37.0
Total	100	100.0

A total of 100 students were questioned, of which 63 were females and 37 were males.

Table 1.1: Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	23	23.0
21-23	74	74.0
24-26	3	3.0
Total	100	100.0

The age group 21-23 has the highest frequency for self-medication (74%)

Table 1.2: Reason for choosing medicine as profession

Reason	Frequency	Percentage
Own Choice	74	74.0
Parents' Choice	26	26.0
Total	100	100.0

Subject's own choice is the major reason behind choosing medicine as profession.

Table 1.3: M.B.B.S. Year

Year	Frequency	Percent
1st year	13	13.0
2nd year	13	13.0
3rd year	11	11.0
4th year	56	56.0
5th year	7	7.0
Total	100	100.0

The majority of the students that took part in the survey were from 4th year of M.B.B.S (56%)

Figure 1.4: What are antibiotics used for?

Bacterial infection was considered to be the major reason for antibiotics usage.

Figure 1.5: Which of the following statement(s) about medicines is (are) correct?

Broad-spectrum Antibiotics Are Better Than Narrow spectrum Ones	70	72.2%
Higher Doses Result in Faster Recovery	13	13.4%
High Doses Result In Less Adverse Reactions	2	2.1%
Switching Antibiotics Enhances Drug Effects	10	10.3%
Switching Antibiotics Reduces Adverse Reactions	14	14.4%
Intravenous is Better Than Oral Medication	18	18.6%

Table 1.6: Frequency of Self-Medication

Frequency	Frequency	Percent
3 to 4 times	24	24.0
5 times or more	38	38.0
Once or twice	38	38.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1.7: Reason for Self-Medication

Reason	Frequency	Percent
Convenience	89	89.0
Cost Saving	11	11.0
Total	100	100.0

Convenience was the major reason reported for self-medication.

Figure 1.8: For which of the following complains did you use medicines?

Runny nose	49	49.3%
Nasal congestion	23	23.2%
Cough	39	39.4%
Sore Throat	47	47.5%
Fever	57	57.6%
Aches and Pains	47	47.5%
Vomiting	27	27.2%

Fever (57.6%) was the most reported cause for self-medication.

Table 1.9: The selection of medicines based on

Determinant	Frequency	Percent
Opinion of friends	30	30.0
Own Experience	39	39.0
Previous Doctor's Prescription	31	31.0
Total	100	100.0

Subjects own experience was reported to be the major factor in selection of medicines.

Table 2.0: What do you think of medicine for self-health care?

	Frequency	Percent
Acceptable	61	61.0
Good practice	11	11.0
Not Accept	28	28.0
Total	100	100.0

The practice of self-medication was considered acceptable (61%) by the majority of the study population.

The selection of medicine was based on:

According to Age

		Opinion of	Own Experience	Previous D	
Age	18-20	9	5	9	23
	21-23	21	32	21	74
	24-26	0	2	1	3
Total		30	39	31	100

Table 2.1.0

According to Gender

		Opinion of	Own Experience	Previous D	Total
Gender	Female	20	20	23	63
	Male	10	19	8	37
Total		30	39	31	100

Table 2.1.1

M.B.B.S Year

		Opinion of	Own Experience	Previous D	Total
Your M.B.B.S Year	1st year	5	2	6	13
	2nd year	3	5	5	13
	3rd year	5	4	2	11
	4th year	14	26	16	56
	5th year	3	2	2	7
Total		30	39	31	100

Table 2.1.

Figure 2.2: Where did you usually obtain antibiotics from?

Community Pharmacies	79	80.6%
TCM Practitioners	2	2%
Leftover from Previous Prescriptions	16	16.3%
Online Pharmacies	1	1%

Community pharmacies were the major sources from where the medicine was obtained.

Figure 2.3: How did you decide the dosage of medicine?

By Checking the Package Insert	26	26.3%
By Consulting a Pharmacist	14	14.1%
By Consulting Family Members/Friends	15	15.2%
From Internet	4	4%
From Previous Experience	32	32.3%
By Guessing the Dosage	8	8.1%

Most of the subjects (32.3%) decided the dosage from their previous experiences.

How many times did you treat yourself with medicines in the past?

According to Age

		3 to 4 times	5 times or more	Once or twice	Total
Age	18-20	7	6	10	23
	21-23	15	31	28	74
	24-26	2	1	0	3
Total		24	38	38	100

Table 2.4.0

According to Gender

		3 to 4 times	5 times or more	Once or twice	Total
Gender	Female	16	23	24	63
	Male	8	15	14	37
Total		24	38	38	100

Table 2.4.1

M.B.B.S Year

		3 to 4 times	5 times or more	Once or twice	Total
Your M.B.B.S Year	1st year	5	1	7	13
	2nd year	2	7	4	13
	3rd year	1	5	5	11
	4th year	13	24	19	56
	5th year	3	1	3	7
Total		24	38	38	100

Table 2.4.2

What was your reason for self-medication? Check more than one.**According to Age**

		Convenience	Cost Saving	Total
Age	18-20	18	5	23
	21-23	69	5	74
	24-26	2	1	3
Total		89	11	100

Table 2.5.0

According to Gender

		Convenience	Cost Saving	Total
Gender	Female	60	3	63
	Male	29	8	37
Total		89	11	100

Table 2.5.1

M.B.B.S Year

		Convenience	Cost Saving	Total
Your M.B.B.S Year	1st year	9	4	13
	2nd year	12	1	13
	3rd year	10	1	11
	4th year	52	4	56
	5th year	6	1	7
Total		89	11	100

Table 2.5.2

What do you think of self-medication for self-healthcare?**According to Age**

		Acceptable	Good practice	Not Acceptable	Total
Age	18-20	12	5	6	23
	21-23	46	6	22	74
	24-26	3	0	0	3
Total		61	11	28	100

Table 2.6.0

According to Gender

		Acceptable	Good practice	Not Acceptable	Total
Gender	Female	39	6	18	63
	Male	22	5	10	37
Total		61	11	28	100

Table 2.6.1

M.B.B.S Year

		Acceptable	Good practice	Not Acceptable	Total
Your M.B.B.S Year	1st year	7	3	3	13
	2nd year	7	1	5	13
	3rd year	9	2	0	11
	4th year	34	5	17	56
	5th year	4	0	3	7
Total		61	11	28	100

Table 2.6.2

Figure 2.7: Do you think you can treat common diseases with medicines successfully by yourself?

Yes	51	51%
No	10	10%
Not Sure	39	39%

Most of the subjects (39%) think that they can treat common diseases with self-medication.

DISCUSSION:

Self-medication is getting increasingly important in healthcare with the passage of time. [20] Studies show that it is more prevalent amongst medical students. This study finds the prevalence of self-medication among medical students of GMC to be 99% in contrast to a study conducted among medical students in Karnataka (53%), [21] 42% in study conducted in university students of Islamabad and 59% in a non-medical population in a previous study in Nepal. [22]. In our study 84.5% said that they opt for self-medication as it is a convenient source of getting medicine, 11.3% considered it a cost saving activity and 10.3% said that they had other reasons. These observations are comparable with the findings of previous studies which also showed that the most common reasons for self-medication were minor ailments (82%) and lack of time to consult a doctor. Other studies have reported that the reasons as mild illness (40%) and shortage of time to consult a doctor (32%). [23] Self-medication among the students also appears to be influenced by economic factors. This observation agrees with studies done in Sudan and Bogotá.[24,25] In this study it was noticed that the classes of drugs that were commonly used were analgesics (Panadol, paracetamol) and antibiotics (Augmentin, Flagyll, Amoxil). In another study it was reported that the classes of drugs that were commonly used were antipyretics (71%), analgesics (65%), antihistamines (37%) and antibiotics (34%). Another study showed antipyretics (43%), analgesics (81%), antibiotics (6%) and antihistamines (13%) were commonly used.[26] In other studies it was found that medical

students used more types of antibiotics compared to the non-medical students, which may be because of their knowledge about antibiotics.[26] By comparison some studies done in Pakistan and Iran did not show significant differences in self-medication between medical and non-medical students.[26] These observations highlight the geographical and cultural variation in determinants of self-medication. In the study conducted in Karachi, analgesics were the most common (88.3%) followed by antipyretics and antibiotics; the study in Bahrain also reported analgesics to be the most commonly used drug group (81.3%) with antibiotics contributing only 6% of the total share. [27] In our study of all who self-medicate (99%) were of belief that self-medication may harm their health, 1% said that it can't harm their health.

This shows diverse attitude towards self-medication practices suggesting a result-oriented intervention. The practice of self-medication may be a risk factor for later substance misuse, which is especially common in anesthesiology, emergency medicine and psychiatry.[28] Personal and professional development programmers have Though the medical students have the facility to consult the relevant physician at next door, they are reluctant to do it practically. Many a times a false belief that they know the exact etiology and treatment, makes them self-medicate. On one hand self-medication plays an important role in dealing with medical emergencies while on other end it may lead to fatal outcomes. Right from the induction in medical college the medical students start self-medication practices. Not

only this, but they also start providing consultation to their non-medical colleagues and family members which could result into many unwanted results. Multiple studies in medical institutions across the country to assess the knowledge attitude and practices of self-medication and its frequency, should be conducted. Findings of such studies will suggest how to incorporate concepts and principles of responsible self-medication in medical curriculum.

The limitations of this study included the absence of a comparative group, such as students from another field; the small sample size; and the absence of interventions, like providing information regarding hazards of self-medication. This study concludes that majority of the students in GMC (99%), practiced self-medication. Analgesics and Antibiotics (prescription drugs) were the drugs most commonly used. Prior experience and non-seriousness of the illness were the most common reasons for self-medication. This indicates that the practice of self-medication is fairly common amongst medical students; this tendency is facilitated by the easy availability of drugs and information. Inappropriate self-medication has the potential to cause serious harm, not only to the students themselves but also to those whom they suggest medication.

Potential problems of self-medication should be emphasized to the students, to minimize this risk. Restriction of sale of drugs with potentially harmful effects should be implemented effectively. Although the self-medication practice is inevitable; drug authorities and health professionals need to educate students about the pros and cons of self-medication. Practicing self-medication is very common among medical students worldwide. Though the medical students have the facility to consult the relevant physician at next door, they are reluctant to do it practically. Many a times a false belief that they know the exact etiology and treatment, makes them self-medicate. On one hand self-medication plays an important role in dealing with medical emergencies while on other end it may lead to fatal outcomes. Right from the induction in medical college the medical students start self-medication practices. Not only this, but they also start providing consultation to their non-medical colleagues and family members which could result into many unwanted results. Multiple studies in medical institutions across the country to assess the knowledge attitude and practices of self-medication and its frequency, should be conducted. Findings of such studies will suggest how to incorporate concepts and principles of responsible self-medication in medical curriculum.

Limitation of Study: The limitations of this study included the absence of a comparative group, such as students from another field; the small sample size; and the absence of interventions, like providing information regarding hazards of self-medication.

Conclusion

This study concludes that majority of the students in GMC (99%), practiced self-medication. Analgesics and Antibiotics (prescription drugs) were the drugs most commonly used. Prior experience and non-seriousness of the illness were the most common reasons for self-medication. This indicates that the practice of self-medication is fairly common among medical students; this tendency is facilitated by the easy availability of drugs and information. Inappropriate self-medication has the potential to cause serious harm, not only to the students themselves but also to those whom they suggest medication.

Recommendations

- Potential problems of self-medication should be emphasized to the students, to minimize this risk.
- Restriction of sale of drugs with potentially harmful effects should be implemented effectively.
- Although the self-medication practice is inevitable; drug authorities and health professionals need to educate students about the pros and cons of self-medication.

REFERENCES:

1. Jamison AJ, Kielgast PJ, Hoek AJM, Reinstein JA. Responsible Self-Medication. Joint Statement by the International Pharmaceutical Federation and World Self-Medication Industry. 1999; p 16.
2. Afolabi AO. Factors influencing the pattern of self medication in an adult Nigerian population. *Ann Afr Med* 2000; 7(3): 120-127.
3. World Health Organization. Global Strategy for Containment of Antimicrobial Resistance: World Health Organization. Communicable Diseases Surveillance and Response (CRS).WHO/CDS/CRS/DRS/2001.2.2001.
4. Fadara JO, Tamuno I. Antibiotic Self-medication among university medical undergraduates in Northern Nigeria. *J. Pub Health Epidemiol.* 2011; 3(5): 217-220
5. Aswapokee N, Vaithayapichet S, Heller RF. Pattern of antibiotic use in medical wards of a university hospital, Bangkok, Thailand. *Rev Infect Dis* 1990; 12 (1): 136-141.
6. Okeke NI, Lamikanra A, Edelman R. Socioeconomic and Behavioral Factors Leading to Acquired Bacterial Resistance to Antibiotics in

- Developing Countries. *Emerg Infect Dis* 1999; 5(1): 18-27.
7. Erhun WO, Erhun MO. The qualitative impact of broadcasting media advertisement on the perception of medicines in Nigeria. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour* 2002; 3(1): 8-19.
 8. Nancy V, Markm N. Changing Patterns of Pharmaceutical Practice in United States. *Soc Sci Med* 1997; 44(9): 1285-1290.
 9. Hamel MJ, Odhacha A, Roberts JM. Malaria Control in Bungoma District Kenya: a survey of home treatment of children with fever, bed net use and attendance at antenatal clinics. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2001:10-23
 10. Vamil AG. Dangers of Self-Medication, 2005 [cited 2006 April CONCLUSION <http://www.dawn.com>
 11. Brennam G, Troyen A, Leape L, Laird L, Nan M. Incidence of adverse events and negligence in hospitalized patients. Results of the Harvard Medical Practice Study. *England Journal of Medicine* 1997; (4): 370-376.
 12. Johnson J. Level of Knowledge among adolescent girls regarding effect treatment for dysmenorrhea. *J Adolescent Health Care* 1998; 12 (9): 398-406
 13. Laurice LB. Medication error. An expose of the Problem, 2000 [cited 2001 May 4] <http://www.google.com>
 12. Braithwaite A, Pechere JC. Pan-European survey of patients' attitudes to antimicrobial drugs and antibiotics. *J Int Med Res* 1996; 24(4): 229236.
 15. Widayati, A., S. Suryawati, C. D. Crespigny and J. E. Hiller. "Self-medication with antibiotics in Yogyakarta City Indonesia: A cross sectional Population based survey". *BMC Research Notes*, Vol. 4, 2011
 13. "Antibiotic resistance a global threat, WHO", *The Times of India* dated Thursday 1 may 2014.
 14. Joseph, O. F. and Igbiks Tamuno, "Antibiotic self-medication among university medical undergraduates in Northern Nigeria". *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology*, Vol. 3 Issue 5, 2011.
 15. Eric, S. D., Patience B. Tetteh-Quarcoo, Patrick Nartey and Isaac O. Agyeman. "Self-medication Practices with antibiotics among tertiary level students in Accra, Ghana: A Cross sectional study". *International Journal of Environmental Research & Public Health*. Vol. 9, Issue 10, 2012.
 16. Gupta, S., "Emerging Indian OTC Markets". *Apeejay-Journal of Management Sciences & Technology*. Vol.1, Issue 1, 2013.
 17. Hughes CM, McElnay JC, Fleming GF. Benefits and risks of self-medication. *Drug Saf*. 2001; 24:1027-1037
 18. G. K. Nalini. Self-Medication among Allopathic medical Doctors in Karnataka, India. *BJMP* 2010; 3:325.
 19. Shankar PR, Partha P, Shenoy N. Self-medication and no doctor prescription practices in Pokhara valley, Western Nepal: a questionnaire-based study. *BMC FAM Pract*. 2002; 3:17
 20. James H, Handu SS, Khalid AJ, Khaja A, Ootom S, Sequeira RP. Evaluation of the knowledge, attitude and practice of self-medication among first-year medical students. *Med Princ Pract*. 2006; 15:270-275.
 21. Awad, A.; Eltayeb, I.; Matowe, L.; Thalib, L. Self-medication with antibiotics and antimalarial in the community of Khartoum State, Sudan. *J. Pharm. Sci.* 2005; 8, 326- 331.
 22. López, J.J.; Dennis, R.; Moscoso, S.M. A study of self-medication in a neighborhood in Bogotá. *Rev. Salud. Publica (Bogota)* 2009; 11, 432-442.
 23. Sarahroodi S, Arzi A, Sawalha A.F., Ashtarinezhad A. Antibiotic Self-Medication among South Iranian University Students. *International Journal of Pharmacology* 2010; 6(1): 48-52
 24. James H, Handu SS, Al Khaja KA, Ootom S, Sequeira RP. Evaluation of the knowledge, attitude and practice of self-medication among first-year medical students. *Med Princ Pract* 2006; 15:270-5.
 25. Bennett J, O'Donovan D. Substance misuse by doctors, nurses and other healthcare workers. *Curr Opin Psychiatry* 2001; 14:195-199.